

Volumetric, viscometric and refractive index behaviour of *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous dimethylsulphoxide at different temperatures

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Abstract : Densities (ρ), viscosities (η) and refractive indices (n) of aqueous dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) (10% v/v) and of solutions of amino acids [*dl*-valine (Val), *l*-isoleucine (Ile) and *l*-proline (Pro)] (0.01–0.05 M) in aqueous-DMSO were measured at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. The density data have been used to calculate apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), limiting partial molar volume (ϕ_v^0), and the slope (S_v), using Masson's equation. The viscosity data were analysed by means of Jones-Dole equation. The activation parameters of viscous flow, namely, free energies of activation per mole of solvent ($\mu_1^{\ddagger*}$) and per mole of solute ($\mu_2^{\ddagger*}$), respectively, were obtained by using transition state theory. The refractive index data was used to calculate molar refraction (R_m) for all the three amino acids in aqueous-DMSO solvent mixtures. All these parameters are used to study solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in the aforementioned mixtures.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, refractive index, partial molar volume, amino acids.

The physicochemical and thermodynamic properties of amino acids and peptides are of considerable interest, as these biomolecules are the building blocks of all living organisms, and are found to provide valuable information that leads to a better understanding of proteins¹⁻⁴. Since proteins are large complex molecules, the direct study of protein-water interactions is difficult. Therefore, one useful approach is to investigate interactions of the model compounds of proteins, e.g. amino acids and peptides, in aqueous and mixed-aqueous solutions. Some of these interactions are found implicated in several biochemical and physiological processes in a living cell. Recently, there has been increased interest to understand the role of water solvated to soluble organics in the living cells, because of the fact that most biological macromolecules are physiologically active in aqueous solutions⁵. The choice of water for preparing mixed solvent stems from its important and unique role in determining the structure and stability of protein since its presence is known to give rise to hydrophobic forces⁶, which are of prime importance in stabilizing the native globular structure of protein⁷.

The practical importance of mixed solvents has been well recognized in recent years because they provide a

wide range of solvents with appropriate compositions and properties. DMSO is called 'super-solvent' due to its wide range of applicability as solvent in many chemical and biological processes. It has large dipole moment and dielectric constant and is strongly associated aprotic solvent due to highly polar group S=O group in the molecule⁸. It is widely used as cryoprotectant of biological systems⁹. DMSO has also been utilized as an *in situ* free radical scavenger for various cancer treatments¹⁰ and as an anti-inflammatory agent for arthritic condition⁹. Thus, the knowledge of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions of amino acids in aqueous-DMSO medium has its biological significance.

In continuation to our earlier studies¹¹⁻¹³, we report here the densities, ρ , viscosities, η and refractive indices, n of (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04 and 0.05 M) *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous-DMSO (10% DMSO v/v) at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. The density data have been used to calculate apparent molar volume, ϕ_v and limiting partial molar volume, ϕ_v^0 . The viscosity data were analysed by means of Jones-Dole equation. The activation parameters of viscous flow, namely, free energies of activation per mole of solvent, $\mu_1^{\ddagger*}$ and per mole of solute, $\mu_2^{\ddagger*}$, respectively, were obtained by

Table-1 (contd).

using transition state theory. The refractive index data was used to calculate molar refraction, R_m , for all the three amino acids in aqueous-DMSO solvent mixtures. These thermodynamic parameters are used to discuss the solute-solvent/co-solvent and solute-solute interactions in the aforementioned mixtures.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of densities, ρ , viscosities, η and refractive indices, n of (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04 and 0.05 M) *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous-DMSO (10% v/v) at different temperatures are listed in Table 1. The apparent molar volumes of amino acids in aqueous-DMSO were calculated by using the relation,

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho_0} + \frac{M_2}{\rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where C is the molar concentration of the solute (amino acid), ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and the solvent (aqueous-DMSO), respectively and M_2 is the molar mass of the solute. The calculated values of ϕ_v as a function of amino acid concentration and temperature are given in Table 2. The values of ϕ_v were plotted against $C^{1/2}$ and the plots were found to be almost linear in the concentration range studied. These plots are well represented by the equation,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v C^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where the intercept ϕ_v^0 , the limiting partial molar volume

Table 1. Densities, ρ , viscosities, η and refractive indices, n of solutions of *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous-DMSO (10% DMSO v/v) at different temperatures

C (mol L ⁻¹)	T (K)					
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15		
<i>dl</i> -Valine	ρ (kg m ⁻³)					
	0.00	1010.4	1008.8	1007.1	1005.4	
	0.01	1009.7	1007.9	1006.1	1004.3	
	0.02	1010.3	1008.4	1006.4	1004.5	
	0.03	1010.4	1008.5	1006.7	1004.8	
	0.04	1010.9	1009.0	1007.1	1005.1	
0.05	1011.1	1009.2	1007.2	1005.3		
<i>l</i> -Isoleucine	0.01	1010.5	1008.8	1007.1	1005.4	
	0.02	1010.7	1009.0	1007.3	1005.5	
	0.03	1010.9	1009.2	1007.5	1005.7	
	0.04	1011.1	1009.4	1007.6	1005.9	
	0.05	1011.3	1009.6	1007.9	1006.1	
<i>l</i> -Proline	0.01	1010.3	1008.5	1006.6	1004.8	
	0.02	1010.8	1009.0	1007.0	1005.1	
	0.03	1011.3	1009.4	1007.4	1005.5	
	0.04	1011.8	1009.9	1008.0	1006.1	
	0.05	1012.4	1010.4	1008.5	1006.5	
<i>dl</i> -Valine	η (10 ⁻³ Ns m ⁻²)					
	0.00	1.1733	1.0551	0.9517	0.8320	
	0.01	1.1502	1.0239	0.9196	0.8036	
	0.02	1.1594	1.0291	0.9212	0.8068	
	0.03	1.1675	1.0351	0.9253	0.8099	
0.04	1.1763	1.0399	0.9317	0.8131		
0.05	1.1847	1.0443	0.9378	0.8162		
<i>l</i> -Isoleucine	0.01	1.1203	1.0009	0.9001	0.7852	
	0.02	1.1366	1.0110	0.9089	0.7922	
	0.03	1.1512	1.0298	0.9259	0.8057	
	0.04	1.1667	1.0422	0.9359	0.8141	
	0.05	1.1838	1.0516	0.9431	0.5222	
<i>l</i> -Proline	0.01	1.1330	1.0094	0.9064	0.7850	
	0.02	1.1536	1.0183	0.9145	0.7886	
	0.03	1.1694	1.0400	0.9296	0.7990	
	0.04	1.1810	1.0517	0.9401	0.8109	
	0.05	1.1964	1.0594	0.9473	0.8205	
<i>dl</i> -Valine	n					
	0.00	1.3439	1.3433	1.3428	1.3423	
	0.01	1.3432	1.3427	1.3424	1.3420	
	0.02	1.3434	1.3430	1.3427	1.3422	
	0.03	1.3438	1.3435	1.3431	1.3425	
	0.04	1.3440	1.3436	1.3433	1.3428	
	0.05	1.3442	1.3439	1.3435	1.3430	
	<i>l</i> -Isoleucine	0.01	1.3442	1.3439	1.3432	1.3428
		0.02	1.3445	1.3440	1.3334	1.3429
		0.03	1.3448	1.3443	1.3438	1.3432
0.04		1.3451	1.3449	1.3443	1.3439	
0.05		1.3454	1.3450	1.3447	1.3445	
<i>l</i> -Proline	0.01	1.3486	1.3472	1.3462	1.3459	
	0.02	1.3490	1.3476	1.3465	1.3462	
	0.03	1.3494	1.3478	1.3469	1.3467	
	0.04	1.3499	1.3482	1.3472	1.3469	
	0.05	1.3508	1.3490	1.3479	1.3472	

Table 2. Apparent molar volumes, ϕ_v ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous-DMSO (10% DMSO v/v) at different temperatures

C (mol L ⁻¹)	T (K)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15
	<i>dl</i> -Valine			
0.01	1.8522	2.0534	2.1562	2.2593
0.02	1.2089	1.3595	1.5108	1.5979
0.03	1.1594	1.2604	1.2956	1.3442
0.04	1.0357	1.1117	1.1632	1.2398
0.05	1.0209	1.0820	1.1434	1.1771
	<i>l</i> -Isoleucine			
0.01	1.1993	1.2706	1.2926	1.3048
0.02	1.1498	1.2012	1.2281	1.2550
0.03	1.1333	1.1682	1.1867	1.2053
0.04	1.1251	1.1517	1.1710	1.1804
0.05	1.1202	1.1418	1.1536	1.1655
	<i>l</i> -Proline			
0.01	1.2384	1.4386	1.6397	1.7419
0.02	0.9415	1.0421	1.1928	1.2943
0.03	0.8425	0.9430	1.0439	1.1120
0.04	0.7931	0.8687	0.9198	0.9711
0.05	0.7436	0.8421	0.8652	0.9263

of amino acid (which is a measure of solute-solvent interaction), and slope, S_v (which accounts for solute-solute interaction) were obtained by the least-squares fitting of ϕ_v values to the above equation. The values of ϕ_v^0 , along with the slope S_v , are listed in Table 3. The trends observed in ϕ_v^0 values of amino acids are due to their hydration behaviour. The hydration behaviour of amino acids in water is found to comprise of the following interactions¹⁴⁻¹⁹:

- The terminal groups of zwitterions of amino acids, NH_3^+ and COO^- are hydrated in an electrostatic manner, whereas, hydration of the intervening backbone depends on its nature that may be hydrophobic, hydrophilic or amphiphilic.
- Electrostriction of NH_3^+ group is about 10 times greater than COO^- group.
- The overlap of hydration of co-spheres of terminal NH_3^+ and COO^- groups and of adjacent groups results in volume change. The ϕ_v^0 values increase due to reduction in the electrostriction at terminals and it decreases due to disruption of side group hydration by that of the charged end.

A perusal of Table 3 reveals that the values of ϕ_v^0 are

Table 3. Limiting partial molar volumes, ϕ_v^0 , slope, S_v , limiting partial molar volumes in water, $\phi_{v,\text{water}}^0$, volume transfer (from water to aqueous-DMSO), $\phi_{v,\text{tr}}^0$, Falkenhagen coefficient, A , Jones-Dole coefficient, B and free energy of activation per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^{\text{tr}\#}$ and solute, $\Delta\mu_2^{\text{tr}\#}$ for *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous-DMSO (10% DMSO v/v) at different temperatures

Parameters	T(K)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15
	<i>dl</i> -Valine			
ϕ_v^0 ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	1.806	2.031	2.166	2.280
S_v ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3/2} \text{ L}^{1/2}$)	-0.184	-0.219	-0.237	-0.252
$\phi_{v,\text{water}}^0$ ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	0.910	-	0.911	0.917
$\phi_{v,\text{tr}}^0$ ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	0.896	-	1.255	1.363
A ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.3726	-0.4763	-0.5477	-0.5248
B ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	1.9209	2.0108	2.1996	2.0535
$\Delta\mu_1^{\text{tr}\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	9.82	9.72	9.62	9.43
$\Delta\mu_2^{\text{tr}\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	298.18	318.45	351.77	337.05
	<i>l</i> -Isoleucine			
ϕ_v^0 ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	1.250	1.360	1.394	1.418
S_v ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3/2} \text{ L}^{1/2}$)	-0.623	-1.035	-1.120	-1.168
$\phi_{v,\text{water}}^0$ ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	1.058	-	1.065	1.070
$\phi_{v,\text{tr}}^0$ ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	0.192	-	0.329	0.348
A ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.8099	-0.8931	-0.9217	-0.9464
B ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	3.9123	4.1073	4.1367	4.1640
$\Delta\mu_1^{\text{tr}\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	9.82	9.72	9.62	9.43
$\Delta\mu_2^{\text{tr}\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	566.50	603.74	617.13	630.04
	<i>l</i> -Proline			
ϕ_v^0 ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	1.558	1.823	2.163	2.312
S_v ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3/2} \text{ L}^{1/2}$)	-3.855	-4.770	-6.147	-6.581
$\phi_{v,\text{water}}^0$ ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	0.826	-	0.831	0.836
$\phi_{v,\text{tr}}^0$ ($10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	0.732	-	1.332	1.476
A ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.6425	-0.7853	-0.8233	-0.9600
B ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	3.4019	3.7789	3.7552	4.1172
$\Delta\mu_1^{\text{tr}\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	9.82	9.72	9.62	9.43
$\Delta\mu_2^{\text{tr}\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	500.00	564.10	573.66	636.23

large positive for all the three amino acids in aqueous-DMSO. This may be due to reduction in the electrostriction at the terminal groups because of the presence of hydrophobic group in the side chain of these amino acids and also due to strong amino acid-DMSO interactions. The ϕ_v^0 values are in the sequence: Ile < Pro < Val, which is also the order of the size of the side chain (hydrophobic group) of the three amino acids under study, i.e. the increase in ϕ_v^0 may be attributed to the increased hydrophobic/nonpolar character of the side chain of these amino acids causing a reduction in electrostriction at the terminal charged groups. Similar trends in ϕ_v^0 with increasing

size of the side chain of amino acids in aqueous solution have also been reported by Banipal *et al.*²⁰. The ϕ_v^0 values (Table 3) increase with increase in temperature for all the three amino acids studied. This increase can be explained by considering the size of primary and secondary solvation layers around the dipolar ions. At higher temperatures the solvent from the secondary solvation layer is released into the bulk of the solvent, resulting in the expansion of the solution²¹ as inferred from greater ϕ_v^0 values at higher temperatures.

The S_v values, as expected, are found to be negative (Table 3) for all the three amino acids studied and the negative values follow the order : Val < Ile < Pro. The negative S_v values indicate weak solute-solute interactions in these systems. Generally, negative S_v values are associated with solutes showing an overall hydrophobic character²², as in the present case. For all the three amino acids studied, S_v values decrease (become more negative) with increase in temperature, indicating a decreased solute-solute interaction in solution with rise in temperature.

The volume of transfer of amino acids from water to aqueous-DMSO, $\phi_{v,tr}^0$ are calculated by using the relation,

$$\phi_{v,tr}^0 = \phi_{v, \text{aqueous-DMSO}}^0 - \phi_{v, \text{water}}^0 \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_{v, \text{water}}^0$ is the limiting partial molar volume of the amino acid in water and its values for the amino acids under study, at 298.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K, have been taken from the literature^{20,23}. The $\phi_{v,tr}^0$ values are summarized in Table 3. A perusal of Table 3 indicates that $\phi_{v,tr}^0$ values are positive and increase with increase in temperature for all the three amino acids studied. When dissolved in water, amino acids cause a decrease in volume of the water due to the electrostriction of water by zwitterionic terminal groups. The observed increase in $\phi_{v,tr}^0$ may be attributed to the decreased electrostriction of water by $(\text{NH}_3^+$ and $\text{COO}^-)$ groups of amino acids in presence of DMSO, because of the interaction of highly polar S=O group of DMSO with the polar end groups, particularly, NH_3^+ group, of amino acids. Similar explanation for increasing positive $\phi_{v,tr}^0$ values of glycine, alanine, and serine in aqueous glycerol solutions were also proposed by Li and coworkers²⁴. The increase in $\phi_{v,tr}^0$ values with rise in temperature may be due to release of some solvent molecules from the solvation layers, resulting in an expansion in volume of the solution.

The viscosity data were analyzed by using Jones-Dole²⁵ equation,

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (4)$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity of the solution, η and η_0 are the viscosities of solution and the solvent (aqueous-DMSO), respectively, A and B are the Falkenhagen²⁶ and Jones-Dole²⁵ coefficients, respectively. Coefficient, A accounts for the solute-solute interactions and B is a measure of structural modifications induced by the solute-solvent interactions^{27,28}. The values of A and B have been obtained from the intercepts and slopes of the plots of $[(\eta_r - 1)/C^{1/2}]$ vs $C^{1/2}$. The values of A and B are included in Table 3. Table 3 shows that the values of A -coefficients are negative whereas those of B -coefficients are large positive, suggesting weak solute-solute and strong solute-solvent interactions in the amino acid solutions under study. Thus, the values of coefficients A and B support the behaviour of ϕ_v^0 and S_v , which all suggest stronger solute-solvent interaction as compared to solute-solute interactions in these amino acid systems. The variation of B -coefficient with temperature, dB/dT is found to provide direct evidence regarding structure-making or structure-breaking ability of the solute in solution. The dB/dT is negative for structure-maker and positive for structure-breaker²⁹. The dB/dT are positive for all the three amino acids studied, indicating that these amino acids act as structure-breakers in aqueous-DMSO solvent.

Furthermore, the viscosity data were also examined in the light of transition state theory of the relative viscosity proposed by Feakins *et al.*^{27,29}. According to this theory the coefficient B is given as,

$$B = \frac{[(\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0) + \bar{V}_1^0 (\Delta\mu_2^0 - \Delta\mu_1^0)/RT]}{1000} \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{V}_1^0 (= \phi_v^0)$ and \bar{V}_2^0 are the limiting partial molar volumes of the solute (amino acids) and the solvent (aqueous-DMSO), respectively. The free energy of activation per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^{\#}$ has been calculated by using the Eyring viscosity³⁰ relation,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{\#} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (6)$$

where h and N are the Planck's constant and Avogadro number, respectively. Eq. (5) rearranges to give free energy of activation per mole of the solute, $\Delta\mu_2^{\#}$

Table 4. Molar refraction, R_m ($10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of *dl*-valine, *l*-isoleucine and *l*-proline in aqueous-DMSO (10% DMSO v/v) at different temperatures

C (mol L ⁻¹)	T (K)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15
	<i>dl</i> -Valine			
0.00	3.7888	3.7889	3.7903	3.7917
0.01	3.7883	3.7900	3.7938	3.7966
0.02	3.7917	3.7949	3.7994	3.8015
0.03	3.7991	3.8032	3.8061	3.8070
0.04	3.8029	3.8061	3.8103	3.8129
0.05	3.8079	3.8121	3.8157	3.8178
	<i>l</i> -Isoleucine			
0.00	3.7888	3.7889	3.7903	3.7917
0.01	3.7958	3.7991	3.7986	3.8011
0.02	3.8023	3.8037	3.8049	3.8060
0.03	3.8088	3.8103	3.8127	3.8125
0.04	3.8153	3.8198	3.8212	3.8231
0.05	3.8219	3.8243	3.8288	3.8327
	<i>l</i> -Proline			
0.00	3.7888	3.7889	3.7903	3.7917
0.01	3.8397	3.8326	3.8298	3.8337
0.02	3.8454	3.8384	3.8350	3.8393
0.03	3.8512	3.8425	3.8412	3.8465
0.04	3.8580	3.8483	3.8456	3.8499
0.05	3.8683	3.8581	3.8544	3.8551

$$\Delta\mu_2^{\ddagger} = \Delta\mu_1^{\ddagger} + (RT/\bar{V}_1^{\ddagger}) [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^{\ddagger} - \bar{V}_2^{\ddagger})] \quad (7)$$

The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{\ddagger}$ are included in Table 3. It is evident from Table 3 that for all the three amino acids $\Delta\mu_2^{\ddagger}$ are positive and much larger than those of $\Delta\mu_1^{\ddagger}$ in aqueous-DMSO. This suggests that the interactions between amino acids and solvent (aqueous-DMSO) molecules in the ground state are stronger than in the transition state. Hence, in the transition state the solvation of the solute molecules is unfavorable in free energy terms. The values of $\Delta\mu_2^{\ddagger}$ increase in the order: Val < Pro < Ile, indicating that the solvation of amino acids in the transition state becomes unfavorable as the hydrophobic character of the side chain increases from Val to Ile. Thus, the conclusion drawn from $\Delta\mu_2^{\ddagger}$ is in good agreement with those concluded from the trends of ϕ_v^{\ddagger} , S_v and B .

The experimental values of refractive indices (Table 1) show an increasing trend with increasing concentration of amino acids in the solution, indicating that the refractive index is influenced by the interactions in the

solutions. The refractive index data were used to calculate molar refraction, R_m by using Lorentz-Lorenz equation

$$R_m = \left[\frac{(n^2 - 1)}{(n^2 + 2)} \right] \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{x_i M_i}{\rho} \quad (8)$$

where x_i and M_i are the mole fraction and molar mass of i -th component of the mixture. The plots R_m vs C values have been shown graphically in Fig. 1 at 298.15 K. Fig. 1 indicates that R_m values increase almost linearly with increase in the concentration of the solute for all the three amino acids. Since, R_m is directly proportional to mo-

Fig. 1. Variation molar refraction (R_m) with concentration (C) of amino acids in aqueous-dimethylsulphoxide at 298.15 K.

lecular polarizability, from Fig. 2 it is clear that the overall polarizability of the systems under study increases with concentration of the amino acids in the solution.

Experimental

The amino acids, viz. *dl*-valine (Loba Chemie, purity > 99.6%), *l*-isoleucine (s.d. fine chemicals, purity > 99%) and *l*-proline (Thomas Baker, purity > 99%) were recrystallized from ethanol-water mixture and dried over P_2O_5 in a desiccator for 72 h before use. DMSO (E. Merck, Germany, purity > 99.5%) was used as such without further purification, except drying over 0.4 nm molecular sieves. The mixed solvent aqueous-DMSO (10% v/v) was prepared using triple distilled water and was used as solvent to prepare 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and

0.05 M solutions of all the amino acids. The weighings were done on an electronic balance (Precisa XB-220, Swiss make) with a precision of ± 0.1 mg.

The densities of the mixed solvent and the amino acid solutions in mixed solvent were measured by using a single-capillary pycnometer (made of Borosil glass) having a bulb capacity of 8×10^{-3} dm³. The capillary, with graduated marks, had a uniform bore and could be closed by a well-fitting glass cap. The marks on the capillary were calibrated by using triply distilled water. The reproducibility of density measurements was within ± 0.01 kg m⁻³. The viscosities of the mixed solvent and the solutions were measured by using Ubbelohde type suspended level viscometer. The viscometer was calibrated with triply distilled water. The viscometer containing the test liquid was allowed to stand for about 30 min in a thermostatic water bath so that the thermal fluctuations in viscometer were minimized. The time of flow were recorded with a digital stopwatch with an accuracy of ± 0.01 . The viscosity data were reproducible within $\pm 3 \times 10^{-6}$ N s m⁻². The refractive indices of the mixed solvent and ternary solutions of amino acids were measured by using a thermostated Abbe refractometer. The refractometer was calibrated by measuring the refractive indices of triply distilled water and toluene at desired temperatures. The values of refractive index were obtained for sodium D line. The reproducibility of refractive index measurements was within ± 0.0001 s. All the measurements were repeated at least three times for each sample and were found to be reproducible within the precision quoted for the apparatus. The temperature of the test solutions during the measurements was maintained to an accuracy of ± 0.02 K in an electronically controlled thermostatic water bath (JULABO, Model-MD, Germany).

Conclusion :

The trends in the values of ϕ_v^0 , S_v , $\phi_{v, tr}^0$, B , $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for the three amino acids in aqueous-DMSO indicate that in presence of DMSO, there is a reduction in the electrostriction of water at terminal groups of amino acids due to strong amino acid-DMSO interactions. The interactions in these systems follow the sequence : Val < Pro < Ile, which may be due to increased hydrophobic character of the side chain of amino acids.

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